

EFFECTIVE FORMS, METHODS AND TOOLS FOR DEVELOPING PATRIOTISM IN STUDENTS THROUGH ART PEDAGOGY

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Abstract. *The given article provides a comprehensive analysis of the technology for developing patriotism in students through art pedagogy. It also highlights both the theoretical and practical aspects of the topic. It also outlines the scientific and theoretical foundations of the effectiveness of art pedagogy in the educational process, demonstrates how to use these methods effectively, and offers practical recommendations.*

Keywords: *patriotism education, art pedagogy, tools, forms, methods, approaches, educational technology, criteria, national culture, history, values, hermeneutic education, structure of development, components, factors.*

It is important to suggest that at present time in our country, improving the quality of education, preparing highly competitive specialists, clarifying the criteria and indicators for developing high patriotic virtues in students, and systematizing educational materials for developing patriotism in students through art pedagogy are identified as important tasks. The Concept for the Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 highlights the issue of "strengthening the moral-ethical content in higher education, educating young people in the spirit of patriotism based on respect for national values, humanism, and high moral ideals, and further developing the work of strengthening immunity against foreign ideas and ideologies." This requires identifying the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of developing patriotism in students through art pedagogy, refining the content, stages, model, technology, and methodological conditions of this process.

Definitely, in every field, the joy of the achievements of our country, the concern for its prosperity, pride in its nationality, protecting its native land, ancient and modern monuments, achievements in science, culture, and art, sporting successes, material and spiritual wealth, and its timeless values-all of these constitute patriotism. Developing the feeling of patriotism in students and nurturing them in the spirit of love and loyalty to their homeland is a crucial and urgent task.

Besides that, art pedagogy is considered one of the most effective tools for developing patriotism in students. Art pedagogy reflects the process of human artistic development and the formation of a student's cultural identity through art and creative activity in both theoretical and practical contexts. Figure 1 shows the main categories of art pedagogy.

1. Art Pedagogy
2. Visual art
3. Music Art
4. Music Art
5. Literary Art
6. Theatre Art
7. Film Art
8. Design Art
9. Media Art

Figure 1. Main categories of Art Pedagogy

At present time in higher education institutions, measures to instill loyalty to the nations, concern for its fate, and a sense of belonging in students, as well as to develop ideological immunity against foreign ideas and negative attitudes through the integration of art and education, have not been systematically organized. Additionally, the monitoring of the effectiveness of the activities organized in this regard has been insufficient. It is also apparent that the specific mechanisms for organizing moral-educational and patriotic activities have not been established.

Although different scholars from different fields have conducted scientific research related to the development of patriotism in students, the issue of developing patriotism in students through art pedagogy and improving its technology has not been studied specifically. The need to identify the unique characteristics, structure, components, factors, criteria, and indicators of developing patriotism in students through art pedagogy, as well as to develop a process model, pedagogical technology, and software and didactic support, has defined the topic of our research.

Additionally, the process of developing patriotism in students is a complex one, encompassing educational, psychological, and methodological approaches. The structure of this process allows for its step-by-step planning and implementation. In order to systematize the educational and educational process of developing patriotism in students through art pedagogy, we have developed the following framework during the research process.

Figure 2. Framework for developing patriotism in students in the pedagogical process

Within the scope of the research, the structure for developing patriotism in students was clarified based on the analysis of pedagogical, scientific-methodological literature, works of prominent scholars, sources created by researchers on patriotism, and the accepted normative-legal documents.

Certainly, the development of patriotism in students through art pedagogy is closely related to social relations, national and universal values, and the manifestation of limitless love for one's homeland. It involves ability of students to consciously perceive, analyze, and evaluate information, taking into account their existing acquired experiences. From the perspective of personal values, this also implies an uncompromising attitude toward foreign ideas and a readiness to fight ignorance with enlightenment.

In the development of patriotism in students through art pedagogy, it is particularly effective and important to organize work on texts that require a hermeneutic approach. The preparation and promotion of art pedagogical tools, the creation of advertising, flyers, brochures, and other promotional materials, as well as increasing their appeal, are considered highly important for enhancing student interest through hermeneutics.

The hermeneutic teaching technology, along with active and interactive methods (such as role-playing games, training sessions, debates, demonstrations), creates the necessary conditions for students to correctly assess the author's perspective in a text (work) and further clarify their own point of view.

For determining the development of patriotism in students and assess whether they have developed ideological immunity against foreign ideas, practical sessions based on role-playing games and stage performances were organized within the "Art Pedagogy" circle. Discussions and collaborative debates were also held. Texts related to information threats to our art and culture, which form the foundation of patriotism, were selected. These texts expressed forms of behavior inconsistent with social norms defined by society.

In conclusion it is important to suggest that based on the results of the research, the following scientific-methodological recommendations were developed:

1. It is advisable to plan the teaching of the "Art Pedagogy" course within the elective courses block for the pedagogical education direction at higher education institutions and to develop electronic-methodological support for the course.
2. The curricula for pedagogical-psychological subjects should include topics related to developing patriotism in students, strengthening "ideological immunity," protecting against the influence of foreign ideas and "popular culture," and teaching the methodology of intolerance towards destructive ideologies.
3. It is necessary to introduce elective and special courses at all levels of the continuous education system on the concepts of patriotism: the feeling of homeland, longing for the homeland, concern for the homeland, the development of the homeland, and the praise of the homeland.

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